

Breakthrough in Sedative Drug Delivery by Chewing gum - An In Vivo Study

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Abstract

Background - Innovative sedative drug delivery systems in pediatric dentistry enhance the comfort and cooperation of young patients during dental procedures. These advancements focus on optimizing drug administration methods for better efficacy, faster onset, and reduced anxiety.

Aim - To compare and evaluate the efficacy and efficiency of innovative route of sedation with conventional routes by measurement of time, visual analogue scale, pulse rate and oxygen saturation level respectively as anaesthetic premedication in Paediatric dentistry.

Methods - An in vivo study was done to evaluate the efficacy and efficiency of different route of sedative drugs administration. Sixty children within the age group of 5-12 years, with Frankel negative behaviour, who required sedation for minor surgical procedures were selected and equally divided into 4 groups. 3 experimental groups and one control group. Group-1 received oral Midazolam mixed with fruit juice, group-2 received nasal spray of Midazolam, group-3 received Midazolam infused with chewing-gum, and group-4 with no sedation. Time to reach the peak sedation level was analysed, pre and post anxiety level was measured by Visual analog scale. O₂ level and pulse rate was determined by using pulse oximeter.

Results - Midazolam infused with chewing-gum achieves significant sedation outcomes and higher patient acceptance compared to oral and nasal routes and demonstrates superior efficacy and comfort in paediatric dental patients.

Conclusion - The study demonstrated that midazolam infused chewing-gum is an effective and safe method which could be a practical delivery system for sedation in clinical settings, providing a convenient alternative to traditional methods.

Keywords - Midazolam, Nasal Spray, Chewing-gum, Sedation

INTRODUCTION

Sedation has long played a pivotal role in paediatric dentistry, serving as a vital tool to manage anxiety, fear, and uncooperative behaviour in children undergoing dental treatment¹. Traditionally, sedative agents have been administered through oral syrups, nasal sprays, or intravenous injections². Although these methods are effective, they are often associated with several limitations, particularly in young patients. The bitter taste of oral syrups may lead to poor acceptance³, nasal sprays can be uncomfortable or provoke resistance⁴, and intravenous injections are frequently associated with needle-related

anxiety and pain⁵. These challenges can significantly hinder patient compliance and contribute to negative dental experiences.

In response to these drawbacks, the field has increasingly focused on developing alternative, more patient-friendly drug delivery systems. Over the years, advancements in pharmaceutical technology have introduced innovative sedative formulations such as medicated lozenges, jellies, ice creams, and chewing gum⁶. These novel approaches aim

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to enhance palatability, reduce invasiveness, and improve the overall experience for paediatric patients. A key advantage of these formulations is their ability to facilitate drug absorption through the oral mucosa, bypassing first-pass hepatic metabolism and resulting in a more rapid onset of action.

Among these emerging options, medicated chewing gum has garnered particular interest due to its unique combination of pharmacologic and psychological benefits. It allows for efficient sublingual delivery of sedative agents while engaging children in a familiar and non-threatening activity.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

An in Vivo, comparative study was conducted in the Department of Paediatric and Preventive Dentistry to compare and evaluate the efficacy and efficiency of innovative route of sedation with conventional routes as drug delivery system. The study was approved by the institutional ethical committee and informed consent was obtained from the parents or legal guardians of all participants.

A total of 60 children, aged between 5 and 12 years, who required sedation for minor surgical dental procedures, were selected for the study. Based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria, the participants were randomly divided into four equal groups (n = 15 per group):

- **Group 1** : Received oral Midazolam mixed with fruit juice.
- **Group 2** : Received intranasal Midazolam spray.
- **Group 3** : Received Midazolam-infused chewing gum.
- **Group 4** : Received no sedation and served as the control group.

Inclusion Criteria

- Children aged 5–12 years
- Children demonstrating negative behavior according to Frankl's Behavior Rating Scale
- Children with parental consent

Exclusion Criteria

- Children with systemic medical conditions (e.g., cardiac or respiratory disorders)
 - Children weighing less than 10 kg
- To evaluate the efficacy and safety of sedation in pediatric

patients, a Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) (Fig 1) was used to assess anxiety levels before and after the procedure in all the groups (Fig 2 and 3), offering a subjective yet quantifiable measure of emotional response⁷. A pulse oximeter was employed throughout to monitor pulse rate and oxygen saturation in every groups, ensuring early detection of any adverse events. An accurate weighing machine was used prior to drug administration to determine the child's weight for precise dosing. Additionally, a stopwatch was used to measure the onset time of sedation, allowing standardized comparisons across patients and sedative agents.

Fig 1 - Visual analogue scale (VSA) to evaluate the anxiety level

Fig 2 - Pre-Treatment Evaluation done with VSA Scale

Fig 3 - Post Treatment Evaluation Done by VSA Scale

Group 1 (Oral Midazolam Intake with Fruit Juice)

In this group, children were administered Midazolam at a dose of 0.5 mg/kg body weight. To enhance palatability and maintain consistency, the medication was mixed with one-fourth

glass of fruit juice before oral administration, ensuring effective masking of the drug's taste and standardized delivery across all patients. (Fig 4)

Fig 4 - Intake of Midazolam

Group 2 (Nasal Midazolam Spray Administration)

Midazolam was given intranasally at a dose of 0.2 mg/kg body weight. The calculated dose was divided and delivered as two sprays into each nostril, ensuring even distribution and effective absorption through the nasal mucosa. This method allowed for rapid onset and non-invasive administration of the sedative agent. (Fig 5)

Fig 5 - Nasal Midazolam Spray is Administrated

Group 3 (Midazolam Infused with Chewing Gum Administration)

An innovative method was adopted for this group, where Midazolam was delivered via medicated chewing gum. The recommended sublingual dose of 0.2 mg/kg body weight was calculated for each child, drawn into a sterile syringe, and infused into homemade chewing gum (Fig 6). Children were instructed to chew the gum for 3–5 minutes, after which it was discarded. (Fig 7)

Fig 6 - Chewing gum Infused with Midazolam

Fig 7 - Child Getting Sedated by Midazolam Infused Chewing gum

Group 4 : Control Group (No Sedation)

This group received no sedative premedication and served as the control for comparison. Anxiety levels and physiological parameters were recorded before the dental procedure using the same evaluation methods.

Results

The collected data were tabulated and subjected to statistical analysis using appropriate software. Descriptive statistics, ANOVA, and post hoc tests were applied to determine the significance of differences among the groups. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant. The analysis revealed that a reduction in anxiety levels across all experimental groups, with the exception of the control group where no sedation was administered. Among the sedative groups, the greatest reduction in anxiety was observed in the group that received Midazolam infused chewing gum followed by Midazolam nasal spray group while the least reduction was noted in the group where Midazolam was administered orally with fruit juice (Table 1 and Graph 1). Intergroup comparisons demonstrated highly significant differences in anxiety reduction between all the groups. (Table 2)

	Pre Intervention	Post Intervention	Mean Change	F value	P value	Significance
Group I	8.33±1.112	4.93±1.334	3.40±0.910	74.732	0.001	Significant
Group II	8.06±1.091	5.06±1.667	3.00±1.301			
Group III	8.40±0.984	2.86±1.124	5.53±0.991			
Group IV	8.33±0.891	9.06±0.883	-0.73±1.38			

-Sign indicates increase in the anxiety scores, Intergroup comparison done using One Way NOVA

Table 1 – Intergroup comparison of anxiety level in pre and post intervention by one way ANOVA test

Intergroup comparison	Mean Diff	Std Error	P value	Significance
Group I Group II	.40000	.42613	0.352	Non-Significant
Group I Group III	-2.13333*	.42613	0.001	Significant
Group I Group IV	4.13333*	.42613	0.001	Significant
Group II Group III	-2.53333*	.42613	0.001	Significant
Group II Group IV	3.73333*	.42613	0.001	Significant
Group III Group IV	6.26667*	.42613	0.001	Significant

Table 2 – Further intergroup comparison of anxiety level in mean score by Post hoc analysis

Graph 1 – Mean value change in pre and post intervention anxiety level

Similarly on statistical evaluation it was found that the mean time to achieve the desired level of sedation was shortest in the group where chewing gum was used, followed by the group that received intranasal spray, while the longest time was observed in the group administered Midazolam mixed with fruit juice (Table 3 and Graph 2). The intergroup comparison showed statistically significant differences, indicating that the route and method of administration influenced the onset time of sedation (Table 4).

	Mean	Std Dev	Std Error	F value	P value	Significance
Group I	24.66	3.538	0.913	198.115	0.001	Significant
Group II	16.33	1.676	0.432			
Group III	7.60	1.502	0.387			

Table 3 - Intergroup comparison of mean time taken to achieve required sedation level by one way ANOVA test

Intergroup comparison	Mean Diff	Std Error	P value	Significance
Group I Group II	8.333	.88419	0.001	Significant
Group I Group III	17.06*	.88419	0.001	Significant
Group II Group III	8.73*	.88419	0.001	Significant

Table 4 - Further intergroup comparison of mean time to achieve required sedation level by Post hoc analysis

Graph 2 - Mean time taken to achieve sedation in various experimental groups

A similar trend was observed in pulse rate measurements, with a noticeable reduction in post-intervention values across all sedative groups, indicating a calming effect following sedation. (Table 5 and 6)

	Pre Intervention	Post Intervention	Mean Change	F value	P value	Significance
Group I	83.00±5.20	81.46±1.92	1.53±5.84	12.687	0.001	Significant
Group II	84.93±4.49	81.33±2.63	3.60±3.56			
Group III	84.73±4.86	78.00±2.67	6.73±3.10			
Group IV	85.86±3.97	89.53±1.35	-3.66±3.75			

All the values are in multiples of X10³

Table 5 - Intergroup comparison of pulse rate in pre and post intervention groups by one way ANOVA test

Intergroup comparison	Mean Diff	Std Error	P value	Significance
Group I Group II	-2.53333	1.21302	0.048	Significant
Group I Group III	-2.73333*	1.21302	0.028	Significant
Group I Group IV	5.33333*	1.21302	0.000	Significant
Group II Group III	-2.20000	1.21302	0.045	Significant
Group II Group IV	5.86667*	1.21302	0.000	Significant
Group III Group IV	8.06667*	1.21302	0.000	Significant

Table 6 - Further intergroup comparison of pulse rate done by Post hoc analysis

In contrast, oxygen saturation levels remained stable in both experimental and control groups, suggesting that none of the sedation methods compromised respiratory function. (Table 7)

	Pre Intervention	Post Intervention	Mean Change	F value	P value	Significance
Group I	97.33±1.23	97.40±0.82	-0.06±1.33	0.803	0.437	Non-Significant
Group II	97.40±0.91	97.26±0.59	0.13±1.18			
Group III	97.33±0.81	97.53±0.99	-0.20±1.14			
Group IV	97.46±0.83	97.00±0.65	0.46±0.99			

All the values are in multiples of X10³

Table 7 - Intergroup comparison of O₂ saturation level in pre and post intervention groups by one way ANOVA

In case of O₂ saturation level one way ANOVA test was insignificant therefore further post hoc analysis is not required as it would be eventually come insignificant. These findings support the safety and differential efficacy of the various sedation delivery methods used in the study.

DISCUSSION

Administering sedative medications to pediatric patients presents unique challenges. Traditional methods, such as oral syrups, often have an unpleasant taste, leading to resistance among children, while nasal sprays can be intimidating and uncomfortable, as noted by Shanmugavel, Asokan et al. (2016)⁸. To address these issues, innovative approaches like sedative chewing gum have been explored as alternative delivery systems. This method not only offers a more palatable option but also facilitates sublingual drug absorption, potentially enhancing the onset and efficacy of sedation.

One significant benefit of using medicated chewing gum is its ease of administration. Mutsumi Takahashi, Yogetsu bando et al. (2024)⁹ highlighted that it eliminates the need for water or specialized medical equipment, making it particularly suitable for on-the-go scenarios and reducing logistical challenges in various settings. This convenience is especially beneficial in pediatric care, where patient cooperation can be limited. Moreover, Sengul Yaman-Sozbir, Sultan ayaz-Alkaya et al. (2019)¹⁰ found that the act of chewing gum, being familiar and non-threatening to children, helps overcome psychological barriers associated with sedation.

Drugs delivered via medicated chewing gum can be absorbed through the oral mucosa, allowing them to bypass the gastrointestinal tract and first-pass metabolism in the liver. Tick Whai Lim, Shu May Choo et al. (2018)¹¹ reported that this pathway leads to a faster onset of action and improved bioavailability of the medication. Additionally, Shanmugavel et al. (2016)⁸ demonstrated that the dosage can be adjusted by varying the concentration of the drug in the gum or by controlling the duration of chewing, providing flexibility in managing sedation levels.

Research comparing different administration routes of midazolam—a commonly used sedative—suggests that the sublingual route is more effective than oral and nasal routes. Studies by Tick Whai Lim et al. (2018)¹¹ and Shanmugavel et al. (2016)⁸ found that sublingual administration of midazolam resulted in a quicker onset of sedation and greater overall effectiveness compared to other methods, further supporting the potential of medicated chewing gum as a viable delivery system.

Beyond its pharmacological advantages, chewing gum has also been shown to improve perioral muscle strength¹². In a study conducted by Takahashi et al. (2024)⁹, participants engaged in regular gum-chewing exercises over three months, resulting in significant enhancements in tongue and cheek muscle strength. Furthermore, Sengul Yaman et al. (2019)¹⁰ observed that such exercises contributed to reductions in stress, anxiety, and depression, indicating additional psychological benefits.

Several other studies have corroborated these findings. Takahashi et al. (2024)⁹ reported that gum-chewing exercises led to significant improvements in perioral muscle strength, with effects maintained for at least three months after discontinuation of the exercise. Similarly, Shirai et al. (2018)¹³ demonstrated that gum-chewing exercises increased maximum bite force, suggesting enhanced masticatory function. These findings further support the multifunctional benefits of chewing gum beyond sedation.

Despite these advantages, safety considerations must be addressed. J Jacobsen, LL Christrup, NH Jensen, et al (2004) reported a case of acute poisoning in a child who ingested dexmedetomidine-containing chewing gum, emphasizing the need for careful dosing and monitoring when using medicated chewing gum for sedation. This highlights the importance of ensuring appropriate formulations and dosages, particularly in pediatric applications.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the integration of medicated chewing gum as a sedative delivery method presents a promising alternative to traditional routes, particularly in paediatric care. Its ease of administration, combined with pharmacokinetic advantages and additional benefits such as improved perioral muscle strength and psychological well-being, positions it as a viable option for sedation. Midazolam chewing gum facilitates faster and more consistent drug absorption through the oral mucosa, potentially leading to more efficacy and efficiency for sedation. Hence it is recommended as an innovative sedative drug delivery system in pediatric dentistry.

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